

Therapeutic Effect of Combined Colon Clear and Cupping Therapy on Idiopathic Skin Pathology

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Abstract

The study aimed at demonstration of idiopathic skin pathology; influence of *Helicobacter pylori* and therapeutic effect of combined colon clear with cupping therapy.

The complex spectrum of inflammatory skin diseases is ever expanding and evolving particularly in psoriasis, idiopathic eczema and atopic dermatitis. The etiology of these inflammatory atopic dermato-pathological disorders is still obscure but it is basically autoimmune triggered and maintained by an aberrant response of the skin immune system cells. Pro-inflammatory cytokines play a pivot role in the pathogenesis of immune skin pathologies. *H. pylori* could migrate or get forced to migrate to the colon leading to accumulation of profuse toxic amounts of ammonia unopposed or buffered by any acidity. The association of *H. pylori* with autoimmune disorders and chronic idiopathic dermatitis was sufficiently reported. The role played by the increased mucosal production of inflammatory mediators (cytokines) induced by *H. pylori* was also clearly illustrated. Antibiotics are seldom effective against extra-gastric *H. pylori* strains. A potent natural purgative is the only measure to eradicate *H. pylori* strains migrated to the colon. Elimination of toxic metabolites and inflammatory mediators from the body is a challenge which is only feasible via seroclearance blood-let out cupping therapy.

Seven patients with atopic dermatitis, seven with idiopathic eczema and seven with psoriasis were randomly included in the study on the basis of being newly discovered, not starting any definitive treatment and having a frank history of *H. pylori* dyspepsia which was proved by sensitive specific tests. All patients underwent colon clear employing the potent natural senna purge which was followed in five days by a session of blood-let out seroclearance cupping therapy on the upper back.

Marked improvement as regards the scales, itchiness and discoloration was seen in 5 patients with dermatitis, 6 patients with eczema and 4 patients with psoriasis after colon clear. Improvement was much more marked after cupping therapy.

On conclusion, combined natural colon clear and blood-let out cupping therapy should be considered as a potent adjuvant therapeutic measure in idiopathic immune skin disorders associated with *H. pylori*.

Keywords: Cupping therapy; Skin pathology; *H. pylori*

Introduction

The complex spectrum of inflammatory skin diseases is ever expanding and evolving particularly in psoriasis, idiopathic eczema and atopic dermatitis [1]. The etiology of these inflammatory atopic dermatological disorders is still obscure but it is basically autoimmune triggered and maintained by an aberrant response of the skin immune system [2]. Pro-inflammatory cytokines play a pivot role in the pathogenesis of immune skin pathologies [2,3].

Idiopathic eczema is an atopic inflammatory skin disease which has got mostly a chronic relapsing course with seasonal variation and marked influence of emotional stress. The disease affects the quality of life particularly in younger life; itching causes the worst effect on life

mostly in office workers. Diagnosis of chronic eczema represents a medical challenge due to its obscure etiology and wide clinical heterogeneity [4].

Prevalence of immune-mediated conditions such as atopic dermatitis has been observed during recent decades. Atopic dermatitis markedly diminishes the quality of life of affected individuals. Sleep disturbance and impaired productivity in work due to chronic itch impose a socio-economic burden. Conventional therapies for atopic dermatitis are capable of reducing itch symptoms; however, most patients are not satisfied with anti-pruritic effect of conventional therapies [5].

Psoriasis is one of the most prevalent autoimmune skin disorders; its etiologic reasons and pathogenesis, though had been extensively investigated during last decade, is still unclear. Psoriasis represents a common chronic inflammatory disease involving skin, nails and joints

which is characterized by chronic or recurrent skin symptoms with skin itching and scaling [6].

The association of *Helicobacter pylori* with many idiopathic skin disorders through immune or different unknown reasons has been sufficiently reported in literature [7].

Aim

Demonstration of the therapeutic effect of combined colon clear and cupping therapy on atopic skin disorders associated with *H. pylori*.

Design and Settings

Prospective study done in Balghsoon Clinics in Jeddah, Saudi Arabia between October 2011 and May 2013.

Patients and Methods

Seven patients with atopic dermatitis, seven with idiopathic eczema and seven with psoriasis were randomly included in the study on the basis of being newly discovered, not starting any definitive treatment and having a frank history of *H. pylori* dyspepsia which was proved by sensitive specific tests [7].

All patients underwent colon clear employing the potent natural senna purge which was followed in five days by a session of blood-let out seroclearance cupping therapy on the upper back [8,9].

Results

Marked improvement as regards the scales, itchiness and discoloration was seen in 5 patients with dermatitis, 6 patients with eczema and 4 patients with psoriasis after colon clear. Improvement was much more marked after cupping therapy.

Ethical Considerations

An informed signed consent was taken from all patients; they were made aware about safety of the natural remedies employed for them. They were free to quit the study whenever they like.

Discussion

Idiopathic inflammatory skin diseases are prevailing and flaring up during late decades particularly in psoriasis, idiopathic eczema and atopic dermatitis [1]. The etiology of these inflammatory atopic skin disorders is still obscure but it is basically autoimmune triggered and maintained by an aberrant response of the skin immune system cells [2]. Pro-inflammatory cytokines play a pivot role in the pathogenesis of immune skin pathologies [2,3].

H. pylori could migrate or get forced to migrate to the colon leading to accumulation of profuse toxic amounts of ammonia unopposed or buffered by any acidity [7,8]. The association of *H. pylori* with autoimmune disorders and chronic idiopathic dermatitis was sufficiently reported [10]. The role played by the increased mucosal production of inflammatory mediators (cytokines) induced by *H. pylori* was also clearly illustrated [11,12].

The question hence arises; can *H. pylori* induce that pathology shown in Figures 1-3!! *H. pylori* in the colon becomes a poison its self by encoding autoimmunity and becomes a source of poison by producing profuse toxic amounts of ammonia for a purpose or no

purpose [7,8]. These two reasons per se are sufficient to predispose, trigger and maintain the course of idiopathic skin conditions. In addition, different reports in literature have confirmed the association of cytotoxin-associated gene A (*cagA*) positive *H. pylori* strains, and emphasized that *cagA* of *H. pylori* encodes a highly immunogenic and virulence-associated protein; the presence of this virulent gene in the body could affect the clinical outcome in many patients [13]. Therefore, the literature correlates between existence of *H. pylori* and many pathologic skin disorders [7].

Figure 1: Case of atopic dermatitis before natural therapy (colon clear and cupping).

Figure 2: Case of idiopathic eczema before natural therapy.

Figure 3: Case of psoriasis before natural therapy.

The question would arise again; are combined colon clear and cupping therapy capable of inducing that resulting dramatic effective

improvement in idiopathic dermatologic conditions as shown in Figures 4-6!! Colon clear eliminates the toxin and the source of toxins by eradication of *H. pylori* from the colon [14]. Cupping blood-let out therapy helps to eliminate the toxic inflammatory mediators from both tissues and circulation and it also allows rectifying the compromised individual immunity via seroclearance [9].

Figure 4: Case of atopic dermatitis after natural therapy.

Figure 5: Case of idiopathic eczema after natural therapy while.

Figure 6: Case of psoriasis after natural therapy.

It is worthy to mention that antibiotics are seldom effective against extra-gastric *H. pylori* strains [15]. A potent natural purgative is the only measure to eradicate *H. pylori* strains migrated to the colon [14]. It seems also critically important to mention that elimination of toxic metabolites and inflammatory mediators from the body is a challenge which is only feasible via seroclearance blood-let out cupping therapy [9].

Conclusion

Combined natural colon clear and blood-let out cupping therapy should be considered as a potent adjuvant therapeutic measure in idiopathic immune skin disorders associated with *H. pylori*.

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